

Synthesis of 1-Benzothiazol-2-yl-2-arylimino-s-triazolo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazoles

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N-Aryl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(benzothiazol-2-yl)guanidines have been obtained by the reaction of *N*-aryl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-ylthioureas (1) with lead oxide. Oxidative cyclisation of *N*-aryl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(benzothiazol-2-yl)guanidines (2) by lead tetraacetate led to the formation of 1-benzothiazol-2-yl-2-arylimino-s-triazolo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazoles (5).

Heteroaryl guanidines are useful intermediates in the synthesis of a variety of fused heterocyclic systems¹. Heteryl guanidines may be prepared² by the reaction of the corresponding thioureas with lead oxide, followed by the addition of primary amines to the resulting carbodiimides. The preparation of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-yl-carbodiimide, thus required in the synthesis of *N*,*N'*,*N''*-trisubstituted-guanidines has now been undertaken.

N-Phenyl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-ylthiourea³ (1; X = H, Ar = C₆H₅) obtained from 2-aminobenzothiazole and phenyl isothiocyanate, was refluxed with yellow lead oxide in benzene. The reaction mixture

was worked up to give two compounds with m.ps. 214–16° and 298°. On the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data, the first compound (m.p. 214–16°) was identified as *N*-phenyl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(benzothiazol-2-yl)guanidine (2; X = H, Ar = C₆H₅) and the other compound (m.p. 298°) as *N*-phenyl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-ylurea (3; X = H, Ar = C₆H₅) based on spectral data and by comparison with an authentic sample³. The formation of 2 may be explained through the reaction of carbodiimide intermediate (4) with 1 followed by elimination of a molecule of aryl isothiocyanate (Scheme 1). On the other hand, the reaction of 4 with water may give *N*-phenyl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-ylurea (3). The formation of 3 was

Scheme 1

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not observed when the reaction was carried out in the presence of a dehydrating agent like calcium chloride⁴.

A number of *N*-aryl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(benzothiazol-2-yl)guanidines (Table 1) have been prepared by the reaction of 2-aminobenzothiazole, 6-chloro- and 6-methyl-2-aminobenzothiazoles with phenyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-anisyl and *p*-bromophenyl isothiocyanates. The structures of these guanidines were supported by their spectral data and elemental analysis. Surprisingly in all these reactions *N*-aryl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-ylcarbodiimides could not be isolated.

Like amidines^{5,6}, the structurally analogous guanidines may be looked upon, as precursors of novel *s*-triazolo fused heterocycles. Therefore, oxidative cyclisation of *N*-aryl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(hetero-2-yl)-guanidines has now been undertaken.

TABLE 1—M.P. and YIELD OF 2 AND 5

Compd	2 and 5		2 M p (°C)/ (yield%)*	5 M P (°C)/ (yield%)
	X	Ar		
a	H	C ₆ H ₅	214–16 (76)	120–22 (58)
b	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	220–22 (74)	128–30 (55)
c	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	208–11 (68)	106–09 (52)
d	H	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	224–26 (72)	108–10 (51)
e	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	212–14 (72)	100–03 (53)
f	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	210–11 (75)	119–21 (54)
g	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	198–200 (70)	136–38 (56)
h	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	202–04 (71)	112–14 (50)

*In presence of calcium chloride.

A mixture of *N*-phenyl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(benzothiazol-2-yl)guanidine and freshly prepared lead tetraacetate

Scheme 2

in dry benzene was reacted at room temperature. The ir spectrum of the product revealed the absence on NH group. Its molecular ion was observed at m/z 399, i.e. at two mass units lower than that of the starting material. On the basis of spectral data (see Experimental) and elemental analysis, the product may be assigned structure **5** or **6**. 1-Benzothiazol-2-yl-2-phenylimino-*s*-triazolo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazole structure (**5**) over structure **6**, for the product of oxidative cyclisation of **2**, was preferred on the basis of uv data and energy calculations. The uv data of the product (λ_{\max} 304, 280 and 221 nm) are comparable with those⁷ of **7** (λ_{\max} 314 and 274 nm). For structure **6** the longer wavelength absorption maximum, on analogy with the uv absorption⁷ of **8** (λ_{\max} 375, 315 and 262 nm), is expected at above 350 nm. The structure **5** assigned to the product is supported by energy calculations data. The calculation of strain energies using molecular mechanics⁸ has shown that isomer **5** is thermodynamically more stable than isomer **6** by nearly 13 kcal mol⁻¹.

Compounds **2** (Table 1) were cyclised with lead tetraacetate and the products have been assigned the corresponding 1-benzothiazol-2-yl-2-arylimino-*s*-triazolo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazole structure (**5**). The formation of **5** from **2** may be explained by a free radical mechanism⁶ (Scheme 2).

Experimental

N-Aryl-*N'*,*N''*-bis(benzothiazol-2-yl)guanidines (**2**). *General procedure* : A mixture of finely powdered *N*-aryl-*N'*-benzothiazol-2-ylthiourea (0.005 mol), yellow lead oxide (0.01 mol) and calcium chloride (0.3 mol) in benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h. The reaction was stopped when no blackening occurred on addition of a further small quantity of lead oxide. The reaction mixture was then filtered hot. The residue obtained from the filtrate on distilling off the solvent was subjected to chromatography over a column of silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) mixture gave pure guanidine (**2**) : **2a** ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (NH), 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=N);

¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.2 (2H, s, NH), 6.6–7.8 (13H, m, ArH); m/z M^+ 401; **2b** ν_{\max} 3 400 (NH), 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=N); ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.11 (2H, s, NH), 7.25–7.91 (12H, m, ArH), 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃); m/z M^+ 415.

*1-Benzothiazol-2-yl-2-arylimino-*s*-triazolo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazoles (5). General procedure* : A mixture of guanidine (**2**; 0.0025 mol) and freshly prepared lead tetraacetate (0.004 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue was repeatedly extracted with chloroform. The combined chloroform extracts was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified over a column of neutral alumina, eluting with benzene-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) mixture to give pure **5** : **5a** ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 635 cm⁻¹ (C=N); ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 7.0–7.8 (m, ArH); m/z M^+ 399; λ_{\max} (log ϵ_{\max}) 304 (3.06), 280 (3.07), 221 (3.37).

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